

The role of Multimedia Technologies In the Development of Creative Abilities of Students

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ABSTRACT

The use of multimedia technologies opens up new opportunities in the organization of the educational process, as well as in the development of creative abilities of students. The joint efforts of education workers, scientists, programmers, manufacturers of multimedia teaching AIDS and teachers-practitioners create a new information educational environment in which the integration of educational and information approaches to the content of education, methods and technologies of training becomes decisive.

Key words: multimedia technologies, educational process information base, knowledge visualization, interactive interface, demonstration of visual materials, creative thinking, multimedia equipment, electronic learning systems

INTRODUCTION

Trends in the development of the modern system of higher education are inextricably linked with the widespread introduction into the educational process of various forms, methods and means of active learning. One of the leading trends of Informatization of society is the development of multimedia technologies, their penetration into various spheres of social life: production, business, science, education, mass consumer culture. Providing a wealth of content and form, a combination of different types of text, graphics, speech, music, video, photo information and a variety of ways to extract them, these technologies form a multimedia perception of the world. The use of multimedia technologies opens up new opportunities in the organization of the educational process, as well as the development of creative abilities of students. For the effective implementation of active learning methods, a large and serious work is needed to equip a sufficient number of computer equipment, as well as to prepare the methodological and information base in the organization of the educational process. This will ensure the implementation of methods of active training in improving the quality of training, taking into account the increased requirements in the market.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Currently, multimedia technology is one of the most rapidly developing areas of new information technologies in the educational process. The first task is to create such models of knowledge representation in which it would be possible to represent both objects characteristic of logical thinking and images-pictures with which figurative thinking operates by monotonous means. The second task is the visualization of those human knowledge for which it is impossible to find text descriptions. The third is the search for ways of transition from the observed images-pictures to the formulation of a hypothesis about the mechanisms and processes that are hidden behind the dynamics of the observed pictures. Thus, the obvious advantages of the use of multimedia technologies (operational use of information, connection of audio and visual material, etc.) in the organization of the educational process are not in doubt. The use of such technologies significantly activates educational information, makes it more visual for perception and easy for assimilation [1]. The joint efforts of education workers, scientists, programmers, manufacturers of multimedia teaching AIDS and teachers-practitioners create a new information educational environment in which the integration of educational and information approaches to the content of education, methods and technologies of training becomes decisive. The modern education system is increasingly using information technology and computer telecommunications, which contributes to a number of factors, and, above all, - the equipment of educational institutions with powerful computer technology and the development of

the Internet community. The scope of application of computers in teaching and research is vast [2]. It is possible to allocate the following priority questions of integration of computer technologies in educational process:

- psycho-pedagogical cycle;
- systematization of educational computer tools;
- consideration of the role of the global INTERNET in learning.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Each teacher has his own style of work. Someone used to work at the blackboard, someone prefers to explain the material, sitting at his Desk or standing at the chair, someone easier and more familiar to move freely in the audience. But, be that as it may, many teachers are faced with the need to demonstrate visual materials. Lecture and seminar form of training should be combined with modern innovative solutions. The teacher does not act as a distributor of information (as is traditionally accepted), but as a consultant, adviser, sometimes even a colleague of the student [3]. This gives some positive points: students actively participate in the learning process, learn to think independently, put forward their points of view, simulate real situations. The use of multimedia technologies allows the teacher to manage the demonstration of visual material much more effectively, organize group work and create their own innovative developments, while not breaking the usual rhythm and style of work. The multimedia computer for training includes additional equipment: CD-ROM drive, head phones, sound speakers. For demonstrations in the classroom requires a special projector and screen. A wide range of images, the active inclusion of creative thinking in the educational process help the student to perceive the proposed material holistically. The teacher has the opportunity to combine the presentation of theoretical information with the demonstration material. Educational multimedia programs are used for frontal, group and individual training in the classroom, as well as for independent work at home. They offer the user a lot of options for individual customization: the student, mastering the educational material, he sets the speed of learning, the amount of material and the degree of its difficulty. Positive factors that speak in favor of this way of obtaining knowledge are the following:

- Better and deeper understanding of the material being studied.
- Motivation of the student to contact a new area of knowledge.
- Time savings due to a significant reduction in training time.
- The acquired knowledge remains in the memory for a longer period and is later easier to recover for practical use after a brief repetition.

One of the first names of lessons that use computer equipment and software, lessons with computer support (UCP). This term was formed under the influence of the term common in English - speaking countries-CBT (Computer Bases Training) - computer support of training [4].

The widespread use of multimedia later gave rise to a new name for such lessons - "multimedia lesson". For easier pronunciation, the name was shortened and now most frequently used of media lesson. In fact, all three terms can be used in the same sense. Media lesson has its own methodological capabilities and advantages:

- improving the efficiency of the educational process by simultaneously presenting the teacher of theoretical information and demonstration material with a high degree of clarity; the emergence of opportunities to model objects and phenomena; automation of routine operations, etc.;
- the opportunity to teach students to use computer technology to solve educational and labor problems, due to the practical processing of educational information on the computer;
- organization of individual work of schoolchildren, development of their cognitive independence and creativity;
- increase motivation to learn due to the attractiveness of the computer, which increases due to multimedia effects;
- development of visual and imaginative thinking, motor and verbal communication skills of students;
- formation of skills of work with information (to make search, selection, processing, ordering and allocation of semantic groups, building of logical communications, etc.), formation of information culture of school students.

The priority goal of media lessons is the development of students' abilities for productive independent creative activity in the modern information-rich environment. Taking this into account, when developing a media lesson, the teacher sets not only educational tasks on the subject, but in the triad of tasks (educational, educational, developing), additionally allocates tasks for the formation of components of information culture [5]. It can be: development of abilities to select the necessary information, acquaintance to new ways of technical processing of information, formation of practical skills on computer processing of information, etc.

The work of students in the classroom can be organized as follows:

- front-view video fragments, observe changes in objects,
- individually - implementation of practical work, problem solving,
- small groups-implementation of the General educational project, statement of model experiment, etc.
- The structure of the lesson can reflect all the components and links of the learning process, as well as the mandatory alternation of activities at the computer and without it:
- updating (repetition of educational material, primary assimilation of the material) - at the computer and (or) without a computer;

- formation of knowledge, abilities, skills (awareness and comprehension of the block of educational information, fixing of educational material) - at the computer and (or) without the computer;
- application (application of educational material in practice, checking the level of assimilation of the material) - at the computer and (or) without a computer [6].

The choice of optimal organizational forms and methods is left to the teacher. Table 1.1 shows how teaching methods are transformed and supplemented through the use of computer technology and software multimedia. Of course, a skillful combination of traditional and information tools depends on the qualification and skill of the teacher, the methodology that he uses. But the competent use of its tools also depends on the teacher's knowledge of the pedagogical basics of informatization of lessons [7]. The organization of the educational process with the help of multimedia technologies involves the use of special software products, among which are: electronic textbooks; training and testing programs; presentations.

CONCLUSION

Multimedia software implements the following types of educational work:

- view information in audiovisual version;
- a simulation of the theory using exercise;
- control;
- work with a dictionary of terms and concepts;
- work with other components of the complex connected to the local network, simulators.

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